

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MAIN DIRECTIONS AND MODERN APPROACHES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCE

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Abstract

The subject of pedagogical psychology is the study of the psychological regularities of human education. It studies the formation of thinking in students, studies the problems of managing the process of mastering the methods and habits of intellectual activity. It clarifies the factors affecting the success of the educational process, the mutual relations between the teacher and students and relations in the student collective, the individual-psychological differences of students, the psychological characteristics of educational work with children, cases of deviations from the norm that manifest themselves in mental development, etc.

Medical psychology studies the psychological aspects of the doctor's activity and the behavior of the patient. It is divided into neuropsychology, which studies the relationship of mental phenomena with physiological brain structures, psychopharmacology, which studies the effect of drugs on the mental activity of a person, psychotherapy, which studies and uses mental influence means for the treatment of patients, psychoprophylaxis, which works out a system of measures to ensure the mental health of people, and psychohygiene.

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Legal psychology clarifies psychological issues related to the implementation of the legal system. It is divided into forensic psychology, which studies the psychological characteristics of the behavior of participants in the criminal process, criminal psychology, which deals with the psychological problems of the behavior and personality formation of the criminal, the motives of the crime, etc., and correctional psychology, which studies the psychology of the convict in a correctional labor colony, the psychological problems of upbringing using persuasion and coercion methods. Along with all this, one can also mention military psychology, sports psychology, commercial psychology, psychology of scientific creativity, and the psychology of artistic creativity.

If we accept the psychological aspects of development as the basis for classifying the branches of psychology, then a number of new areas appear before us in which the principle of development is implemented in its problems. As one of these, age psychology studies the age characteristics of mental processes, age opportunities for mastering knowledge, factors of personality development, etc. One of the central problems of age psychology is the problem of training and mental development, as well as their mutual dependence.

The psychology of abnormal development or special psychology is divided into pathopsychology, which studies deviations in the process of mental development, mental disorders in various forms of brain pathology, oligophrenic psychology - the science of the pathology of mental development associated with congenital defects of the brain, surdopsychology and typhlopsychology.

If we classify the branches of psychology in terms of psychological aspects of the relationship between personality and society, then we can also distinguish a number of areas of psychology that are combined with the concept of social psychology. In social psychology,

three main problems are studied: group, communication and personality problems.

Each science uses research methods to study its object. Research method

means a set of methods and tools that science uses to study its subject.

Research methods in psychology are related to its methodology. In modern science, methodology is used in three senses:

- 1) General methodology;
- 2) Special methodology;
- 3) Methodology as a set of specific methodological methods.

General methodology refers to the "general philosophical approach, general method of cognition" that the researcher refers to. Specific methodology refers to the set of methodological principles applied in the relevant field of science. When considering methodology as a set of specific methodological methods, psychological research methods are usually clarified. Specific research methodology should be scientific in nature. Here, the criteria that determine the effectiveness of the research, namely the validity of the method, the reliability of the information, etc., should be taken into account. In specific psychological research methods, 4 stages are mainly distinguished.

1) Preparatory stage: at this stage, initial information is collected in various ways.

2) It is of an experimental nature. At this stage, the specific methodology of the research is implemented. That is, empirical facts are collected by applying various methods.

3) Research materials are analyzed quantitatively.

4) Materials are interpreted on the basis of psychological theory. Research methods in psychology are mainly divided into 4 groups.

The first group includes comparative, long-term and complex methods. They are called organizational methods.

The second most extensive group of methods consists of empirical methods of obtaining scientific materials, facts. These include: a) observation and self-observation, experimental methods, b) psychodiagnostic methods, c) methods of analyzing activity processes and products, biographical methods, etc.

The third group of methods includes methods of processing materials. These include:

- 1) quantitative (mathematical-statistical) analysis;
- 2) qualitative analysis.

The fourth group of methods is called interpretative methods. They consist of various variants of structural and genetic methods. With the help of these methods, the structure of the studied mental process, state or property is analyzed or the developmental characteristics at a certain age period are clarified. Psychology combines the data of these sciences and at the same time influences them, becoming a model of the sciences about man. Let us briefly look at the relationship of psychology with other sciences. It is impossible to understand the human psyche and behavior without knowledge of its natural and social existence. Therefore, the study of psychology requires the acquisition of knowledge about human biology, the structure and activity of its higher nervous system. Knowledge about the relationship between mental phenomena and the activity of the central nervous system has found its concrete reflection in the physiology of higher nervous activity. It is no coincidence that when talking about the natural scientific foundations of psychology, it is the laws of higher nervous activity that are referred to. Psychology is closely connected with the history and culture of society. Thus, in the development of higher mental functions in man, the main historical achievement of civilization, the tools of labor and the system of signs played a decisive role. Knowledge about the foundations of sociology also allows for a deep study of the human psyche and its understanding. The rapid development of social psychology confirms this once again. In modern times, social psychology penetrates all areas of human relations, allowing us to clarify how human social behavior is acquired through mental properties. Psychology has a serious kinship with the science of philosophy. This is no coincidence. As is known, psychology began to take shape within philosophy before it became an independent science. Undoubtedly, it would be impossible to determine and study the psychological "dimensions" of personality without referring to philosophical knowledge about man, his specific life conditions, perception of reality and activity. Consciousness, thinking and other mental phenomena are not given to people innately, ready-made. They are acquired in the process of training and upbringing of a person in ontogenesis (in the process of individual development). From this it becomes clear that psychology has a connection with the science of pedagogy. The main connection between the sciences of psychology and pedagogy is connected with the proximity of the subjects of these sciences. First of all, the object of these sciences is a developing person (child and elderly). On the other hand, psychology stud-

ies the laws of development of the human psyche. Pedagogy, on the other hand, develops the laws of management of personality development.

Human upbringing, education and training means the purposeful development of his psyche, thinking, and activity. One of the factors indicating the important mutual relationship between the sciences of psychology and pedagogy is the similarity in their research methods. Many scientific psychological searches can play the role of a tool for solving pedagogical problems. As a scientific discipline, psychological knowledge is used in pedagogy to explain, interpret, and systematize pedagogical facts. In modern times, a close relationship between psychology and linguistics has also begun to occupy a wide place. We see a clear manifestation of this in the emergence of psycholinguistics.

Psycholinguistics is a field of science that involves the complex study of speech behavior by psychologists and linguists. Compared to linguistics and the psychology of speech, psycholinguistics has its own independent subject of research. Psycholinguistics is more often considered "its own" by psychology. True, there is a field in psychology that has existed for a long time - the psychology of speech. The subject of speech psychology coincides with the object and subject of psycholinguistics. Therefore, these two disciplines are often confused with each other. Although there is a basis for such identification, there are also aspects that distinguish these two terms from each other. Their difference is mainly manifested in the subject of study. While psychology focuses its attention more on the characteristics of the mental functions of consciousness during the formation, understanding and formation of speech, psycholinguistics also tries to take into account the means of expression (verbal and non-verbal) of these functions in people's speech activity and speech behavior. Psycholinguistics is a relatively young science. It arose approximately in the late 50s and early 60s of the 20th century. The "father" of the Soviet psycholinguistics school was A.A. Leontyev. Psychology 16 Due to the expansion of the field of science, various areas of psycholinguistics have emerged. These include general psycholinguistics, special psycholinguistics, social psycholinguistics, and age psycholinguistics (ontolinguistics). The main fields of psychology. Psychology is a multidisciplinary science. In modern times, there are various fields of psychology that are developing relatively independently. That is why it would be more appropriate to use the term "psychological sciences" rather than "psychological science". Thus, every 4-5 years we witness the emergence of a new field of psychology. Various principles are used to classify the numerous fields of psychology. First of all, psychological disciplines can be classified as fundamental and applied, general and special. The fundamental or basic fields of psychology are fields aimed at interpreting psychology and human behavior in a way that everyone can understand, regardless of their identity and the field of activity they work in. These fields of psychology provide the same necessary information for all people interested in psychology and human behavior. Due to this universality, this field of psychology is used under

the name "general psychology". As for the applied areas of psychology, these include its areas directly applied to practice. The general areas of psychology pose and solve development problems that are equally important for all scientific directions without exception.

As for the special areas of psychology, it sets itself the goal of studying any one or several groups of phenomena. The following three principles are also used in the existing literature to classify modern psychological disciplines: 1. According to specific areas of activity; 2. According to psychological aspects of development; 3. According to the attitude of a person to society. Since it is impossible to cover all of these areas, let us briefly consider some of them that are directly related to education. The most fundamental area of psychological science is general psychology. General psychology or incorporates fundamental psychological knowledge. The global issues that general psychology is interested in and must solve, the questions it must answer are the following: What is the psyche? What are its structure and functions? What regularities does the psyche have in phylogenesis and ontogenesis? What are the levels of development of the psyche and according to what criteria can they be determined? What is the relationship between the psyche and the brain? What is the role of innate and acquired biological and social factors in mental development? What are the criteria that distinguish normal and abnormal development of the psyche? In addition to studying problems related to the psyche as a whole, general psychology is also engaged in the study of specific issues related to mental processes, mental states and properties. Since the main object of psychology is a person, general psychology primarily focuses on the investigation of issues related to his (a person's) personality, activity, communication with cognitive processes, system of relationships (feelings) and volitional activity, volitional regulation, studying them both theoretically and experimentally. From what has been said, it is clear that general psychology reflects generalized knowledge about mental phenomena that is of equal interest to everyone. By becoming familiar with this knowledge, every person can master the general secrets of psychology. Let us consider some of the special areas of psychology that are closely related to education, training and upbringing. One of the important special areas of psychology that is related to specific activities and has high practical importance is pedagogical psychology. Pedagogical psychology studies the psychological problems of training, upbringing and pedagogical activity. The most important problems that pedagogical psychology must solve are to reveal each sensitive period of children's lives and determine all the opportunities necessary for their development during that period, to reveal the mutual relationship between training and development, to clarify the general and age-related aspects of training and upbringing, their relationship, to investigate the psychological regularities that ensure the effectiveness of training and upbringing, etc. Another important area of psychology that is closely related to pedagogical psychology is age psychology. Age psychology studies the dynamics, regularities of mental development in a person from birth to the end of his life, the characteristics of the develop-

ment of mental processes and properties of the personality in ontogenesis. Age psychology has such sections as child psychology, adolescent psychology, youth psychology, adult psychology, old age psychology, and longevity psychology (gerontopsychology). Differential psychology is one of the special fields of psychology. Differential psychology is a branch of psychology that studies, interprets, and explains the individual psychological and behavioral differences of people. The main method of differential psychology was tests. In the early periods, these tests were individual tests, then group tests appeared, and later projective tests were created and used. Genetic psychology can also be attributed to special fields of psychology. Genetic psychology studies the hereditary mechanism of psyche and behavior, their dependence on genotype. Age psychology, differential and genetic psychology together form the scientific basis for understanding the laws of mental development of a child. One of the areas of psychology that attracts the most attention in modern times is social psychology. Social psychology is a scientific field that studies the system of interpersonal relations in a certain social group in the process of joint activity and communication, the reflection of this system of relations in the psychology of the group as a whole, as well as of the individual. Such knowledge is necessary for the psychologically correct organization of education. Legal psychology, one of the important areas of psychology, considers the study of legal norms and rules of behavior by a person, clarifies psychological issues related to the implementation of the legal system. It has sections such as forensic psychology, criminal psychology, correctional psychology, etc. Medical psychology can be noted as one of the areas of modern psychology that has taken a special place. Medical psychology studies the psychological aspects of the doctor's activity and the patient's behavior, his hygiene, prevention, diagnostics, treatment, examination and rehabilitation. Medical psychology includes clinical psychology, pathopsychology, neuropsychology, somatopsychology, general medicine, psychiatry, psychoprophylaxis and psychohygiene, psychocorrection, etc. Pathopsychology, as well as psychotherapy, serves to work with people who have defects in their psyche and behavior. The main task of these areas of psychology is to identify the causes of the existing mental disorder and ways to eliminate it. As for psychodiagnostics, which is one of the new areas of modern psychology, it deals with the theory and practice of assessing the developmental characteristics of people's mental properties, processes and actions with the help of scientifically verified methods that allow obtaining substantial information about them. In conclusion, it should be noted that we have briefly familiarized ourselves with only a part of modern psychology here. Sports psychology, labor psychology, art psychology, space psychology, management psychology, experimental psychology, ethnic psychology, etc. areas of psychology also have their own subjects and tasks. Undoubtedly, it is beyond the scope of this resource to provide detailed information about all of them here.

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